

Challenges for On-Site Automated Ultrasonic Phased Array Inspection of Composite Aircraft

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Extended Abstract

1.1. Introduction

Aircraft maintenance represents 10-20% of the overall operating cost [1], and heavy C-check and D-check maintenance demands NDT inspection of 100% skin area of composite material fuselages. Delamination and low velocity Barely Visible Impact Damages (BVID) are typical in-service damages found in skin causing small to large sub-surface damages with little or no surface indication [2]. These damages are difficult to detect during manual visual inspection. Conventional manual ultrasonic and advanced Phased Array (PA) scanning of skin followed by data interpretation and analysis for damage sizing is time consuming and cost-inefficient for on-site application; hence a potential task to be automated or robotized. Automated PA inspection by magnetic-adhesion based manipulators, crawlers and scanners have led to rapid inspection rates and lowering the cost of inspection in oil and gas sectors. The composite skin surfaces are painted, smooth and non-magnetic, which invalidates the use of current magnetic adhesion based crawlers for inspection. Despite some previous efforts, the development of automated PA inspection of skin surfaces using a mobile robot is still an unsolved problem [3].

This work is a part of ongoing EU-H2020 project 'CompInnova' which aims to develop an integrated NDT approach using combined PA and Infrared Thermography inspection of the fuselage-skin through separate inspection modules mounted on a mobile robot, that will lead to cost-effective combination for on-site automated inspection. A novel vortex based wheeled mobile robot was developed for traversing over the fuselage using adhesion forces generated by means of Electric Ducted Fan (EDF) motors [4]. This robot was designed to carry a PA NDT module [4], but with restrictions on payload (1 Kg.) and minimum water couplant usage requirements. Thus this work presents the development challenges of the PA module for automated PA inspection and to meet the requirements for its integration with robot. PA inspection results obtained by robotic scanning of laminates with impact damages, are evaluated for assessing the functionality and performance of the PA module.

1.2. PA module development

In general, PA module for automated scanning consist of a suitable PA transducer mounted on a positioning fixture, an efficient wedge to transfer ultrasonic wave from transducer into the specimen, encoder for capturing position data, couplant distribution system and a communication controller between robot and PA hardware for data acquisition and scanning control. The most challenging design requirement of PA module here, is the restriction of free flowing water or local immersion as coupling mechanism during inspection. This challenge is addressed by the design of new wedge of elastomer material having low attenuation and low acoustic impedance and dimensions optimized for 10 MHz PA transducer and along with mist (water) based couplant. The development of a pressurized water-pump for delivery of mist (water) through a 100 μm nozzle addresses the need of uniform wetting and couplant distribution, thus minimizing the amount of water sprayed. PA transducer must maintain both normal incidence to both flat and curved fuselage surfaces and have constant contact between the PA transducer and the inspected surface throughout the scan in all orientations. This requirement is achieved by customization of a spring loaded positioning fixture with specific degrees of freedom and a lightweight nylon holder for the PA transducer-wedge assembly. The PA module is developed in a modular fashion with selection of appropriate off-the-shelf components to minimize development time and costs. A virtual keyboard-based communication controller based on a micro-controller is developed for control of PA pulser-receiver hardware. The microcontroller board receives communication from the robot computer station to start/stop data acquisition and storage, which in turn responds with appropriate keyboard commands to PA pulser-receiver. This microcontroller also controls the mist-couplant delivery pump through a relay circuit. Some of the developed hardware components of the PA module is shown in Fig.1(a-c).

Fig.1(a) PA transducer& new elastomer wedge (b) spring-loaded positioning-fixture carrying the transducer wedge & encoder(c) PA module assembled with robot [5] & mist-nozzle mounted in transparent spray guard.

1.3. Results

The NDT experiments using the developed PA module was carried out in three inspection phases; in the first phase, C-scans of flat laminates were obtained by mounting PA module on an X-Y manipulator for fine-tuning. In the second phase, C-scans as shown in Fig. 2(a, b), were captured through preliminary integration of the PA module with the robot. The resulting C-scan images are post-processed by damage detection and sizing algorithms and compared for accuracy and repeatability. In some cases slight misalignment was observed due to robot motion-path, resulting in error in damage sizes as shown in Fig. 2. In the third phase, which is on-going, inspection trials are being planned on curved fuselage structure with full integration of PA module with robot.

Fig. 2 Time of Flight C-scans of the same of BVID on a laminate (9 layers) captured during automated scanning using the robot (a) single line scan (b) raster scan consisting of two line scans

1.4. Conclusion

During the development process the PA module components were revised, updated and preliminary integration with robot was achieved. Performance trials has been achieved on representative composite laminates with impact damages to validate the functionality and performance and the PA module is practical enough for on-site automated scanning on composite surfaces.

1.5. Funding & Acknowledgements

The work is funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 FET-OPEN under RIA Grant No. 665238 CompInnova. This work was developed in partnership with Andrikopoulos G. from research team of Nikolakopoulos, G. Control Engineering Group Lulea° University of Technology, Sweden and Spyridon Psarras and George Sotiriadis from research team of Vassilis Kostopoulos Applied Mechanics & Vibrations, University of Patras, Greece.

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- Keywords: NDT; Ultrasonic Phased Array; Composite structures; Automated Inspection